

Shoots and Tuberos Root Quality of Orange Fleshed Sweet potato [*Ipomoea batatas* (L) Lam] as Affected by Harvest Stages at Adami Tullu, Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia

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Abstract

An experiment was conducted at Adami Tullu Agricultural Research Center in 2018 to determine the effect of the harvest stage on the leaf, vine, and tuberos root quality of orange-fleshed sweet potato varieties. The experiment consisted of four harvest stages (105, 120, 135, and 150 days after planting) and three varieties (Kulfo, Tulla, and Guntute). A four-by-three factorial experiment arranged in RCBD was replicated three times. Leaf dry matter, vine dry matter, tuberos root dry matter, ash, flour moisture, and crude fiber content were collected. The interaction of harvest stage and variety significantly influenced ($P < 0.01$) tuberos root dry matter content and ash content ($P < 0.05$). Vine dry matter content and leaf dry matter content were significantly affected by the main effects of harvest stage and variety ($P < 0.01$). The highest mean values of ash (5.72%) were scored by the Guntute variety harvested at 105 DAP and the highest mean values of tuberos root dry matter content (29.70%) and crude fiber (8.16%) were recorded by the Kulfo variety harvested at 150 DAP. Farmers of the study area and areas having similar agro-ecologies can grow the Guntute variety by harvesting at 135 DAP to obtain a paramount quality of shoots and tuberos roots.

Keywords: Ash, beta carotene, crude fiber, dry matter.

1. INTRODUCTION

Sweet potato [*Ipomoea batatas* (L.) Lam] belongs to the family Convolvulaceae and genus *Ipomoea* (Chang et al., 2010). Globally, it is the seventh crop after wheat, rice, maize, potato, barley, and cassava (Van Jaarsveld et al., 2005; Lebot, 2009; Ahn et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2011; Markos and Loha, 2016). Wider adaptability and beta carotene contents are special attributes of orange-fleshed sweet potato varieties (Trancoso-Reyes et al., 2016). Globally, sweet potato has the third largest cultivated root crop after potato and cassava (Neela and Fanta, 2019). It is cultivated in over 120 countries worldwide (Sugri et al., 2017). Africa and Asia are the leading producers of the crop. Sweet potatoes are tolerant to drought and heat, considered a resilient crop (Laurie et al., 2013). Production of 112.8 million tons (in 115 countries) was reported in 2017, and China is the leading producer, followed by Sub-Saharan African countries (Anonymous, 2019). Asia (75.1%), Africa (20.8%), America (3.3%), Oceania (0.08%), and Europe (0.1%) are regions that shared production from 2007 to 2017 (Anonymous, 2019).

Sweet potato covers about 62,116 hectares of land, providing an annual tuberos root production of 1.6 million tons during the main growing season (Anonymous, 2021). It is a healthy food as it competes nutritionally with all the staple foods. It is ranked highly in terms of complex carbohydrates, protein, vitamins A and C, iron, calcium, starch, phenolic compounds, and antioxidants (Ebregt et al., 2004; Reynolds et al., 2015; Baba et al., 2018; Neela and Fanta, 2019). Orange-fleshed sweet potato is valued for its beta-carotene, a precursor of vitamins A, B6, and C (Robertson et al., 2018). Root stores starch, which is of major economic importance as food, and is consumed in a boiled form, which is one of the cheapest sources of vitamin A. Leaves and vines are used as feed for livestock, and sometimes they are used as a vegetable for human consumption. Orange-fleshed sweet potato varieties have been popularized in Ethiopia to

eliminate micronutrient deficiencies, vitamin A deficiency, and malnutrition problems (Tofu et al., 2007; Kidane et al., 2013; Gurmu et al., 2015). In Ethiopia, these varieties have not been tested at different harvest stages.

The optimum harvest stage is important for the quality of shoots (leaf and vine) and tuberous root. The optimum harvest stage varies among varieties, environmental conditions, and market demand. Dry matter content is the principal component of sweet potato quality, and these parameters of quality vary throughout tuberous root development stages (Woolfe, 1992; La Bonte, 2000) as well as between varieties (Hagenimana et al., 1999). The crop is commonly harvested 150 days after planting, but there is variability in maturity stages among varieties (Alvaro et al., 2017). Harvesting vines at 105 DAP gave optimum production of above-ground fresh biomass without reducing the yield of tuberous roots (Ahmed et al., 2012). Alvaro et al. (2017) concluded that the dry matter content increases with increasing stage of maturity at harvest.

In Ethiopia, preliminary trials, national variety trials, and variety verification trials were done at the Hawassa Agricultural Research Center and various institutions. As a result, promising varieties have been identified, and research on some identified varieties with different plant spacing and fertilizer trials was done at the Adami Tullu Agricultural Research Center. However, basic information on how shoots and tuberous root quality of this crop are affected by harvest stage, variety, and their interaction is still limited. This calls for further studies to be conducted in the Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia. Therefore, the study was conducted to assess the influence of the harvest stage on shoots and the tuberous root quality of orange-fleshed sweet potato at the Adami Tullu condition.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Description of the Study Area

A field experiment was conducted at Adami Tullu Agricultural Research Center (Horticulture research site) located in the Central Rift Valley of Ethiopia, Oromia National Regional State, East Shoa Zone, in the main cropping season from June to October 2018 under supplementary irrigation. The geographical location of the site is at 7° 9' N latitude and 38° 7' E longitude and an altitude of 1650 meters above sea level. It is far away, 168 km south of Addis Ababa, the capital city of Ethiopia. The area has minimum and maximum average annual temperatures of 12.6°C and 27°C, respectively, and received bimodal and unevenly distributed average annual rainfall of 760 mm. Rainfall extends from February to September with a dry period from May to June, which separates the preceding short rains from the following long rains. The pH of the soil is 7.88. The soil texture is fine sandy loam with sand, clay, and silt in proportions of 34, 48, and 18%, respectively (Anonymous, 1998).

2.2. Experimental Materials

Three varieties (Kulfo, Tulla, and Guntute) were grown at the Adami Tullu Agricultural Research Center from June to October 2018 during the main season, and supplementary irrigation was used twice a week during the rainfall was terminated.

Table 1. Description of the varieties used for the experiment

Varieties	Growth habit	Year of release	Altitude	Maturity days	Flesh colour	Yield tone ha ⁻¹	Center of release
Kulfo	Semi compact	2005	1200-2200	150	orange	27	Hawassa
Tulla	Semi compact	2005	1200-2200	150	orange	28.5	Hawassa
Guntute	Semi compact	1997	1500-1800	120-150	orange	34.5	Hawassa

Source: Ministry of Agriculture Crop variety registration bulletin (1983-2017).

2.3. Treatments and Experimental Design

The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. A factorial combination of four harvest stages (105, 120, 135, and 150 DAP) and three orange-fleshed sweet potato varieties (Kulfo, Tulla, and Guntute) were used. The gross size of the experimental plot was 3×3 m (9 m²), accommodating five rows, and a spacing of 60 cm between rows and 30 cm between plants was used. The net sampling plot size was 2.4×2.7m (6.48m²) in all the cases, in which the two outermost rows and one plant at both ends of the row were considered as borders leaving three middle rows with a length of 2.7m for data collection and measurement.

2.4. Experimental Procedure and Field Management

Land preparation was done at the beginning of May with a tractor, harrowed, and leveled before planting. The three-month-old cuttings were transplanted at a row spacing of 60 cm and a plant spacing of 30 cm. Transplanting was conducted on the first date of June 2018. All other necessary agronomic management practices, like watering, earthing

up, cultivation, weeding, and crop protection measures, were carried out uniformly as recommended. The experimental plot was supplemented by furrow irrigation during off-rain.

2.5. Data Collection and Measurement

2.5.1. Quality Parameters

The following quality parameters were randomly collected from plants of net plots at respective harvesting stages (105, 120, 135, and 150 DAP).

2.5.1.1. Leaf Dry Matter Content: Leaf dry matter per plant was estimated by taking 100 g of fresh leaf weight of the plants from each sample at respective harvest stages. The sample was dried in an oven with dry forced air circulation at 70°C for 72 hours. Then the dried sample was weighed by sensitive balance (Model No. yt-1002 and reading scale 0.01). Finally, the dry leaf weight was divided by the fresh leaf weight and multiplied by 100 to get the leaf dry matter in percentage.

2.5.1.2. Vine Dry Matter Content: Vine dry matter per plant was obtained by taking 100 g of fresh vine weight of the plants from each sampled at respective harvest stages and was dried in an oven-dry forced air circulation at 70°C for 72 hours. Then the dried sample was weighed by sensitive balance (Model No. yt-1002 and reading scale 0.01). Finally, the dry vine weight was divided by the fresh vine weight and multiplied by 100 to get the vine dry matter in percentage.

2.5.1.3. Tuberos Root Dry Matter Content: To calculate tuberos root dry matter content, the first 100 g of fresh tuberos roots were prepared from marketable categories of tuberos roots randomly taken from each harvested plot at respective harvest stages, and tuberos roots were sliced, chopped, composited, and dried in an oven with forced air circulation at 70°C for 72 hours. Then the dried sample was weighed by sensitive balance (Model No. yt-1002 and reading scale 0.01). Finally, the dry tuberos root weight was divided by the fresh tuberos root weight and multiplied by 100 to get root dry matter in percentage.

$$\text{Dry matter percentage (DM \%)} = \frac{\text{Dryweightofsample}}{\text{Freshweightofsample}} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (5)}$$

2.5.1.4. Ash content: The ash content was determined by heating a flour sample in a muffle furnace (Anonymous, 2005) at Jimma University College of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine (Postharvest Laboratory). Five grams of flour samples were weighed and transferred to a furnace at 550°C for eight hours. After heating, the ash was weighed and expressed as a percentage of the original sample weight on a dry weight basis.

$$\text{Ash (\%)} = \frac{M3-M1}{M2-M1} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (6)}$$

Where **M1** = Weight of the crucibles; **M2** = Weight of fresh flour sample and crucibles; **M3** = Weight of ash and crucibles.

2.5.1.5. Flour Moisture Content (FMC %): The flour moisture contents of the experimental samples were determined according to AOAC (2005) method 925.09 at Jimma University College of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine (Postharvest Laboratory). The empty dish with its lid was dried in the oven (Leicester, LE67 5FT, England) for 15 min and then transferred into desiccators for cooling before it was weighed to the nearest milligram. About 5 g of the sample was transferred to the dish, and then the dish was placed inside the oven (Leicester; LE675FT; England) at 103°C to dry the samples to a constant weight, cooled in desiccators, and re-weighed. Then, the moisture content was estimated by the following formula:

$$\text{FMC (\%)} = \frac{M2-M1}{M2} * 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (7)}$$

Where **M1** = Mass of sample after drying and **M2** = mass of sample before drying

2.5.1.6. Crude fiber (CF %): The crude fiber was determined at Jimma University College of Agriculture and Veterinary Medicine (Animal Nutrition Laboratory) using dilute acid and alkali hydrolysis using Fibertec (2010) by the Wende method. Exactly 1.5 g of the sample was accurately taken into a glass crucible, about 200 ml of boiled 1.25% H₂SO₄ was poured into the flask, and the mixture was boiled for 30 minutes under a reflux condenser. The insoluble matter was washed with boiling 4 times until the residue was free from acid. About 200 ml of boiling 1.25% KOH solution was added to the residue and then heated for 30 minutes under a reflux condenser. The residue was filtered and washed with boiling water, and then the crucible was transferred to the cold extraction unit and washed with acetone. After digestion, the residue was dried at 105°C in a conventional air oven and cooled in desiccators until constant weight was obtained. The residue was incinerated in an electric furnace at 525°C until all the carbonaceous matter was burnt. The crucible was left to cool down to below 250°C, then removed from the furnace and transferred to the desiccators,

cooled to room temperature, and weighed. The crude fiber was calculated and expressed as a percentage (Anonymous, 2005).

$$\text{Crude fiber (\%)} = \frac{M1-M2}{W} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation (8)}$$

Where **M1** = Mass of the crucible (the sand and wet residue); **M2** = Mass of the crucible (the sand and ash); **W** = Sample weight dry matter basis.

2.6. Data Analysis

Collected data were subjected to analysis of variance using the Genstat 15 edition (Genstat, 2012), and interpretations were made following the procedure described by Gomez and Gomez (1984). Whenever the effects of the treatments were found significant, the means were compared using the least significant difference (LSD) test at a 5% level of significance.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Effects of harvest stage on tuberous root dry matter content of orange fleshed sweet potato

The highest tuberous root dry matter content (29.70%) was recorded by the Kulfo variety harvested at 105 DAP, which was statistically at par with the Guntute variety harvested at 105 DAP (29.33%) (Table 2). The least tuberous root dry matter content was recorded by the Guntute variety (19.73%) harvested at 120 DAP. Tuberous root dry matter accumulation increased as the harvesting stage was delayed (Monamodi et al., 2003). According to Vimala and Hariprakash (2011), data on the dry matter content of eight clones for three seasons showed that tuberous root dry matter increased significantly from 75 to 90 DAP when the maximum tuberous root dry matter occurs during this period and tends to deteriorate after that, and at 105 days, the dry matter content in the majority of the clones decreased. Tuberous root dry matter content of about 27% was obtained when the crop was harvested either at 105 or 120 DAP, which was about 4% higher than when the crop was harvested at 90 DAP (Alcoy^o et al., 1993). Tuberous root dry matter content increased from planting to harvest up to 150 DAP but 180 DAP (Alvaro et al., 2017). Similarly, decreasing tuberous root dry matter content towards harvest was reported by Bhagsari and Ashley (1990). A higher tuberous root dry matter percentage was obtained at 150 DAP (41.6% and 23.4%), and this was higher than the dry matter recorded at 90 DAP, but not at 120 DAP (Shigwedha, 2012). Jahan et al. (2009) also concluded that there is a significant effect of the harvest stage on the dry matter content of tuberous roots. This implies that when sweet potato is harvested at 150 DAP, it receives maximum vegetative growth, as well as the development of tuberous roots, which aids maximum photosynthesis, and hence the accumulations of dry matter in the tuberous roots were higher. The average dry matter content in sweet potatoes is approximately 30%, but it varies depending on cultivar, location, climate, day length, soil type, incidence of pests, diseases, and cultivation practices (Bradbury and Holloway, 1988).

Table 2. Interaction effects of harvest stage and variety on tuber dry matter content of orange fleshed sweet potato at Adami Tullu Agricultural Research Center in 2021

Varieties	Harvest stages	Tuber dry matter content (%)
Kulfo	Stage 1 (105 DAP)	29.70a
	Stage 2 (120 DAP)	20.47c
	Stage 3 (135 DAP)	21.10c
	Stage 4 (150 DAP)	26.53b
Tulla	Stage 1 (105 DAP)	20.33c
	Stage 2 (120 DAP)	20.50c
	Stage 3 (135 DAP)	20.33c
	Stage 4 (150 DAP)	26.87b
Guntute	Stage 1 (105 DAP)	29.33a
	Stage 2 (120 DAP)	19.73c
	Stage 3 (135 DAP)	20.83c
	Stage 4 (150 DAP)	26.03b
LSD (0.05)		2.22
CV (%)		5.6

Means followed by the same letters within same column are not significantly different from each other at 5% level of probability. CV = Coefficient of variations and LSD = Least significant difference

3.2. Influence of harvest stage on vine and leaf dry matter content of orange fleshed sweet potato

Vine and leaf dry matter content was not significantly influenced by the interaction of variety and harvest stage. However, they were influenced by the harvest stage and variety ($P < 0.01$) main effects. The highest vine dry matter content (16.34%) was recorded at 150 DAP, followed by harvest stages 135 DAP (15.03%) and 120 DAP (15.01%). The least vine dry matter content was recorded at 105 DAP (12.74%) (Table 3). Vine dry matter content played a great role in an increment of above-ground fresh biomass weight, which was proportional to vine length. Vine dry matter content is also significantly influenced by a variety of main effects. The highest vine dry matter content was recorded by the Tulla variety (15.70%), followed by the Kulfo variety (15.40%). The least vine dry matter content was produced by the Guntute variety (13.24%). Tulla and Kulfo varieties could be recommended for animal feeds in the study area and areas with similar agroecologies.

Leaf dry matter content was not significantly influenced by the interaction of variety and harvest stage. It was significantly influenced by the variety and harvest stage main effects. The highest leaf dry matter content (20.46%) was recorded at 150 DAP, whereas the least leaf dry weight was recorded at 105 DAP (15.47%). Leaf dry weight was also significantly influenced by a variety of main effects. The highest leaf dry matter content (18.59%) was recorded by the Guntute variety, whereas the least leaf dry matter was recorded by the Tulla variety (16.63%).

Table 3. Main effects of harvest stage on vine and leaf dry matter of orange fleshed sweet potato variety at Adami Tullu Agricultural Research Center in 2021

Treatments	Vine dry matter content (%)	Leaf dry matter content (%)
Harvest stages		
Stage 1 (105 DAP)	12.74b	15.47c
Stage 2 (120 DAP)	15.01a	16.08c
Stage 3 (135 DAP)	15.03a	17.90b
Stage 4 (150 DAP)	16.34a	20.46a
LSD (0.05)	1.58	1.01
Varieties		
Kulfo	15.40a	17.22b
Tulla	15.70a	16.63b
Guntute	13.24b	18.59a
LSD (0.05)	1.37	0.87
CV (%)	10.95	5.92

Means followed by the same letters within same column are not significantly different from each other at 5% level of probability. CV = Coefficient of variations and LSD = Least significant difference.

3.3. Influence of harvest stages on flour moisture, ash and crude fiber contents of orange fleshed sweet potato

Flour moisture ($P < 0.05$), ash ($P < 0.05$), and crude fiber contents ($P < 0.01$) were significantly influenced by the interaction of harvest stage and variety. The highest flour moisture content (7.88%) was recorded by the Guntute variety harvested at 105 DAP. The least flour moisture content was recorded by the Kulfo variety (4.65%) harvested at 105 DAP (Table 4). The flour moisture content at 120 DAP of harvest was lower than those harvested at 90 DAP (Kalu, 2018). Flour moisture content decreased at later harvest due to an increase in fiber and carbohydrate contents. The varieties having low flour moisture content are very important to maintain long shelf life.

The highest ash content (5.72%) was recorded by the Guntute variety harvested at 105 DAP, followed by the Kulfo variety harvested at 105, 120, 135 & 150 DAP, the Tulla variety harvested at 135 & 150 DAP, and the Guntute variety harvested at 120, 135 & 150 DAP. The last ash content (4.05%) was recorded by the Tulla variety harvested at 105 DAP,

statistically at par with the same variety harvested at 120 DAP (4.13%) (Table 4). Kalu (2018) reported an increase in ash content at 120 DAP of harvest for the two varieties at different spaces. The high ash content of the variety indicates that the variety is rich in minerals and they could be recommended to children and lactating mothers since it shows micronutrient contents of the sweet potato. A significant increase in ash content of all the varieties: the CEN variety increased from 0.27% to 0.53%, the NRSP variety increased from 1.06% to 1.31%, and the 87 variety increased from 0.54% to 1.26% at 90 and 150 DAP, respectively (Onyemachi et al., 2018).

Crude fiber content was influenced by the interaction of harvest stage and variety. The highest crude fiber content (8.16%) was recorded by the Kulfo variety harvested at 150 DAP, followed by the Guntute variety harvested at 105 DAP and at 150 DAP. The least crude fiber content was recorded by the Kulfo variety (1.62%) harvested at 105 DAP. According to Kalu (2018), fiber content was higher at 120 DAP of harvest than at 90 DAP of harvest. This indicates that reduced moisture content and maturity favor increased fiber at the delayed harvest stage. The fiber content for all the varieties studied increased with increasing harvesting stages; the NRSP variety increased from 1.20% to 1.55%, the CEN variety increased from 0.56% to 0.67%, and the 87 variety increased from 0.63 to 0.77 at 90 and 150 DAP, respectively (Onyemachi et al., 2018). Varieties having moderate crude fiber are ideal to be added to foods for children.

Table 4. Interaction effects of harvest stage and variety on average flour moisture, ash and crude fiber contents of orange fleshed sweet potato at Adami Tullu Agricultural Research Center in 2021

Varieties	Harvest stages	Flour moisture (%)	Ash (%)	Crude fiber (%)
Kulfo	Stage 1 (105 DAP)	5.60bcd	5.23ab	1.62f
	Stage 2 (120 DAP)	5.30cde	4.73ab	4.21de
	Stage 3 (135 DAP)	5.12de	4.39ab	4.95cd
	Stage 4 (150 DAP)	4.65e	4.45ab	8.16a
Tulla	Stage 1 (105 DAP)	6.30b	4.05b	2.17f
	Stage 2 (120 DAP)	6.03bc	4.13b	2.81ef
	Stage 3 (135 DAP)	5.67bcd	4.83ab	4.85cd
	Stage 4 (150 DAP)	4.95de	5.05ab	5.80cd
Guntute	Stage 1 (105 DAP)	7.88a	5.72a	6.41abc
	Stage 2 (120 DAP)	5.22de	5.00ab	6.23bc
	Stage 3 (135 DAP)	5.60bcd	5.06ab	5.80cd
	Stage 4 (150 DAP)	5.39cde	4.84ab	7.72ab
LSD (0.05)		0.80	0.82	0.97
CV (%)		8.3	10.1	11.4

Means followed by the same letters within same column are not significantly different from each other at 5% level of probability. CV = Coefficient of variations and LSD = Least significant difference

4. Conclusion

The quality of sweet potatoes is affected by different harvest stages. The highest tuber dry matter content (29.70%) was recorded by the Kulfo variety harvested at 105 DAP. The highest mean of ash content (5.72%) was recorded by the Guntute variety harvested at 105 DAP. The highest crude fiber content (8.16%) was recorded by the Kulfo variety harvested at 150 DAP. Since the present experiment was conducted under rain-fed conditions with supplementary irrigation, over-location under irrigation conditions was suggested.

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